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Report on the Current State of Societal Biases in Slovak AI

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Report on the Current State of Societal Biases in Slovak AI

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1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) as a technology is becoming more and more common in our everyday lives, from mobile applications, through social media and websites to various business applications. The current paradigm of AI depends on the use of large volumes of *data* that are often collected from the Web. However, such *wild data* **can often reflect and contain various societal biases** (such as *sexism* or *racism*) that people have; and the AI systems can in fact *learn* these biases and propagate them further. Societally biased systems **can cause various harms to marginalized communities, facilitate unfair treatment of certain groups, or reinforce existing stereotypes**. A biased AI system scoring CVs can give lower scores to certain applicants and harm their chances of employment, a biased chatbot can generate stereotypical statements that undermine the dignity of its users, a biased speech-to-text model can yield higher error rates for certain groups, and so on.

For this reason, AI researchers search for ways to *detect, measure, and mitigate* societal biases in AI systems. **The ultimate goal is to make the AI systems more fair¹ for everyone**. This is not a trivial task – among other things, the AI systems of today are often extremely complex, the underlying deep learning models are impossible to fully understand, and the data used to train them is in practice untraceable. Despite these difficulties, societal bias was already discovered in AI systems performing machine translation, sentiment analysis, curriculum vitae analysis, language generation, and other tasks (Stanczak & Augenstein, 2021).

Most of the work in this field has been done with the English language so far, and as such, it mainly reflects the U.S. culture. In this work, we want to build on these efforts, and **we investigate how biases permeate Slovak AI systems** – AI systems that work with the Slovak language in one way or another. This document serves as a concluding report of our project *Societal Biases in Slovak AI* running from November 2022 to October 2023. The goal of our project was to understand how **gender biases in particular** affect Slovak AI systems, but also to increase the awareness of this issue in both the expert community and the general public, as this is an issue that affects virtually everyone using modern communication technologies.

¹ *Fairness* is a fundamental concept of *trustworthy AI*, a framework dedicated to fostering the ethical, secure, and reliable use and development of AI. The key term of this report – *bias* – is regarded as an element that can potentially undermine fairness. We are aware that these terms may carry slightly different meanings in various fields, but for the sake of clarity, we adopt a generalized interpretation.

Our aim was to approach this issue from an interdisciplinary point of view. The team included people with technical expertise in AI and natural language processing; but also AI ethics experts, social scientists, translators, and gender experts.

The main contribution of our project is the evaluation of multiple types of AI systems, namely English-to-Slovak machine translation systems, Slovak masked language models, and Slovak speech-to-text systems. We have proposed and implemented an evaluation methodology and observed **whether these systems exhibit biased behavior with respect to gender**. Each experiment was aimed at a specific type of biased behavior, such as *male as norm* behavior, stereotypical thinking, or non-equitable performance. Worryingly, we were able to discover some sort of problematic behavior in **all the models** taken into consideration.

We have also published all the data and code, following the principles of *open science*. This ensures that other researchers can reproduce or even improve our work. The datasets and methodology we have developed are in general readily applicable to many other languages. The impact of our project can therefore go beyond only the Slovak language and the Slovak culture.

Contents of this report

This report consists of several standalone chapters that can be read on their own, and it is not necessary to read the entire report to understand the contents.

- **Chapter 2** provides an executive summary of this report and presents the main findings and conclusions of the project. It can be read to ascertain what the main outcomes of our project are at glance.
- **Chapter 3** introduces the issue of *fairness* in AI and provides a brief *theoretical* background for our research. It introduces and discusses terms such as fairness, bias, equality, algorithmic harms and others.
- **Chapter 4** is an invited chapter written by gender experts Mariana Szapuová and Janka Kottulová. The chapter discusses what gender stereotypes are, how they impact our society and language.
- **Chapter 5** describes the experimental research we conducted. It documents how we evaluated the presence of gender biases in various Slovak AI systems, introduces the results, and discusses the implications of what we have found.

- **Chapter 6** documents a data ethics assessment performed during the project to ensure that our research on sensitive issues is as ethical as possible, taking into consideration the needs and points of view of all the stakeholders.

Note on *gender binarism*

For the purposes of this project we consider only the two binary genders, *male* and *female*, and we omit other genders. This is motivated by several factors. First, there is a general lack of data, such as voice recordings, for other genders. Second, we use grammatical gender as a signal for some of the systems. For now, there is no generally accepted way for Slovak grammar to reflect other genders. We believe that studying biases for these genders is an important future work.

Note on terminology

- **AI model** – An *AI model* is the part of an *AI system* that is based on AI technology, nowadays typically a *deep learning* model. As such, an *AI model* needs to be integrated into a system before it is deployed and used.
- **AI system** – An *AI system* is a computer information system that uses *AI models* to perform predictions, generate responses, process data, etc. The behavior of the underlying *AI model* determines the outputs of the system.
- **Bias** – By *bias* in this report, we understand a *societal bias*, a behavior of *AI systems* that can be considered systematically unfair or otherwise harmful towards certain groups of people or even individuals.
- **Gender bias** – *Gender bias* is a type of *societal bias* that is associated with a concept of gender in society. In this report we focus on the two binary genders – *male* and *female* – but gender bias also involves non-binary genders.
- **Slovak AI** – By *Slovak AI* we understand *AI systems* or *models* that are used to process texts written in Slovak language or Slovak speech. As such, the *models* are trained with data created by Slovak people and thus might reflect biases from the Slovak culture.

References

Stanczak, K., & Augenstein, I. (2021). [A Survey on Gender Bias in Natural Language Processing](#) (arXiv:2112.14168). arXiv.

2. Executive Summary

We identified the following premises as our starting point:

- The usage of AI systems in daily lives or in business environments has seen a rapid increase recently.
- AI systems trained on wild data gathered from the Web can and will obtain behavioral patterns that can be explained as societally biased. Gender bias is one such behavioral pattern.
- With this in mind, there is a growing need to understand, detect, identify and measure how strong these biases are.
- There is almost no research about these biases in Slovak AI systems.

Based on this concerning state of matters, we have conducted a research project during which we experimentally evaluated various Slovak AI systems. We present the following main findings in this report:

- **Overall, we were able to discover at least one type of biased behavior in all the models we have studied.**
 - The biased behaviors we detected can be considered unfair or harmful towards at least one of the genders.
- We have evaluated **4** machine translation systems and found out that:
 - All systems have a **strong *male as norm* biased behavior**. They predominantly use the masculine gender when translating English-to-Slovak, while the feminine gender is suppressed.
 - All systems worryingly **deviate from this behavior when exposed to stereotypically female sentences**, such as sentences about beauty, housework or family.
- We have evaluated **4** masked language models and found out that:
 - **3 very popular models display a concerning level of stereotypical behavior**. The models use gender stereotypes when exposed to situations requiring to select the gender of a word.
 - **The one model that does not show stereotypical behavior has a strong *male as norm* biased behavior** and will select words with the *masculine* gender 10 times more often.
- We have evaluated **3** speech-to-text models and concluded that they are **consistently more likely to make errors for female voices**.

Based on our findings, we draw the following conclusions:

- **The behavior of existing Slovak AI systems is gender-biased.** This might cause unfair behavior toward certain groups of people and in extreme cases can even cause them unwanted harm.
- **AI developers** that develop and deploy these systems **should be aware of this issue**, and they **should perform bias evaluation** before deploying AI systems for public use. **The results of these tests should be made publicly available.**
- **The general public should be informed about this issue** and should demand that AI systems do not exhibit problematic forms of behavior.

We present the following main outcomes:

- This **report** documents our work and provides information about the main findings. This report is intended to provide information for both the general public and AI experts. One of its main goals is to increase awareness of the issue. Additionally, the report also provides a general overview of our project and can be used by researchers to analyze our work and results.
- The **methodology** we developed and used in this project is novel and scientifically valuable. We will describe and publish the methodology in a follow-up scientific paper. We believe that it can be reused for other types of biases and other languages as well.
- The **data** we have collected for various types of AI systems can be used by AI developers to measure and tackle the bias in their systems, as well as by other researchers. All the data are published and freely available. Although we focus on the Slovak language, the data can be reused to study this issue in other languages as well.
- Data and code from this project are available at GitHub:
<https://github.com/kinit-sk/biases-in-slovak-ai/>

3. Fairness in AI

This chapter delves into the concept of fairness within the realm of AI ethics and technology. It emphasizes the pivotal role of fairness in mitigating harm and discrimination within AI systems, addressing various forms of bias and their consequences. Furthermore, it provides a brief overview of the legal considerations related to fairness in the European Union and Slovakia, and examines the gender disparity in AI. In essence, the text underscores the paramount importance of fairness in establishing trust, fostering accountability, and contributing to a more equitable society in the field of AI. The inclusion of this chapter in the report aims to offer a deeper insight into the motivations driving the study of gender bias in AI, particularly in light of the imperative of fairness as a foundational element of the concept of *Trustworthy AI*, which is also explained in this chapter.

The concept of *fairness* is not universally uniform. It takes on diverse interpretations depending on individual or group perspectives, largely influenced by their moral beliefs. In the aftermath of World War II, particularly in the Western world, fairness became closely intertwined with the notion of equality. While interpretations of equality may vary, it serves as one of the guiding values that still influence the understanding of fairness within modern democratic societies².

Equality as a fundamental concept demands that every person, regardless of their differences or circumstances, should receive equal respect, dignity, and consideration. However, equality goes beyond the equal distribution of goods and chances and is understood more as *equity* that provides fair opportunities for everyone to fulfill their human potential. In modern democratic societies, the principle of equality should play a pivotal role in advancing social justice, upholding human rights, and combatting discrimination and bias. It acts as a guiding force in shaping laws, policies, and societal norms that aim to build equitable and inclusive communities where every individual has the opportunity to thrive.

The imperative of ensuring fairness in the operation of AI technologies cannot be overstated. **It is essential that these AI systems align with the ethical principles and**

² The European Union. Treaty of Lisbon, Article 1a “The Union is founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. These values are common to the Member States in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity, and equality between women and men prevail”.

values that define our society. The demand for fairness is prominently evident in the framework of the *Trustworthy AI* concept, as elucidated in the publication "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" (EGTAI, 2019) by the *High-Level Expert Group on AI*, established by the European Commission in 2018. *Trustworthy AI* comprises three crucial dimensions – adherence to legal obligations, resilience in both technical and social contexts, and alignment with ethical principles. This multifaceted approach is imperative because AI systems, even when designed with good intentions, can inadvertently inflict harm. Moreover, the concept of trustworthiness extends beyond the AI systems as technological artifacts. It encompasses all stages of their development cycle and various stakeholders that participate or are affected by them.

Fairness entails the equitable and just treatment of individuals, devoid of any discrimination. It encompasses the provision of just opportunities and ensuring recourse for those whose rights have been infringed upon. Thus, fairness as equality embodies a dual nature: one facet revolves around treating everyone impartially, while the other revolves around ensuring redress for those subjected to unfair treatment (EGTAI, 2019).

Fairness assumes a central role in the pursuit of research, development, deployment, and use of trustworthy AI systems for several compelling reasons. It serves for a better understanding of potential biases that can be present in AI systems and helps in devising mitigation strategies against the occurrence of unjust treatment and discrimination. Furthermore, it acts as a shield against the exploitation of bias, ensuring the well-being of affected persons. Embracing fairness enhances transparency and accountability, while a user-centric approach to AI design fosters inclusivity and accessibility for all, irrespective of age, gender, abilities, or characteristics. This commitment extends to ensuring equitable AI access for individuals with disabilities, nurturing a more equitable and trusted AI landscape for our society (ALTAI, 2020).

AI fairness is thus deeply intertwined with the concept of bias. However, the term *bias* can be understood in many ways, whether positive or negative. There are many types of biases, ranging from human biases whether individual or group-based, various statistical biases, and the systemic biases with their direct impact on gender bias that can be present in the form of historical, representation, or societal bias.

Historical bias (Schwartz et al., 2022) refers to biases that have deeply rooted themselves in society over extended periods. It goes beyond just how history is described, extending to how we perceive and interpret it. A common illustration of this bias is the tendency to predominantly view history through a Western or European lens. *Institutional bias* happens when whole institutions, like companies or government agencies, tend to treat certain social groups better or worse because of their rules or practices. For example, when an institution consistently discriminates against certain races or genders, it's called institutional racism or sexism. *Societal bias*, for example, refers to the inclination to favor or discriminate against groups or individuals due to their social identities, demographic traits, or unchangeable physical attributes. They commonly involve stereotypes related to factors like race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status, education, etc.

AI systems can develop biases based on the data they are trained on. Gender stereotypes present in historical data play a role in AI bias as well. AI systems can learn generalized beliefs about different groups from the data they are trained on. For example, if an AI system is trained on biased data that associates certain traits with a particular group, it may perpetuate those stereotypes in its decision-making processes.

Such biases and stereotypes are often deemed unfair. Unfortunately, the answer to the question of whether AI systems could be completely fair is probably negative (Dignum, 2021). This is particularly true for algorithms that learn from data, which already carry many biases. However, that does not mean that we should accept the situation as it is. **We need to better understand the mechanisms behind AI bias and aim to minimize the potential risks before they cause unwanted harm to people.** Dignum argues that the primary issue lies not in bias itself, but rather in prejudice and discrimination. Prejudice denotes a preexisting judgment or attitude, while discrimination refers to actions that manifest such bias. Within society, discrimination frequently occurs through established systems and policies, and it becomes ingrained in cultural beliefs and depictions, inevitably appearing in any gathered data. Consequently, the emphasis should be placed on leveraging AI to bolster efforts aimed at diminishing prejudice and discrimination.

When AI systems exhibit bias, they are essentially making unjustified outputs. These unjustified decisions can have real-world consequences, such as discriminating

against certain individuals or groups when it comes to job opportunities, loans, or legal proceedings.

Even though that bias, stereotype, or prejudice are closely interconnected they still should be deemed as distinct concepts. While bias represents an inclination or preference, either consciously or unconsciously, towards something or someone, stereotypes form generalized beliefs about a group, often oversimplified and based on characteristics. Prejudice involves holding unjustified negative judgments and attitudes towards individuals or groups. Stereotypes often fuel prejudice, and bias reinforces and perpetuates both. This feedback loop can create a harmful cycle in AI systems, leading to unjust outcomes and discrimination. Therefore, it's crucial for developers, researchers, and policymakers to understand and address various forms of unfair bias or discrimination in AI systems. They all should work towards research, development, deployment, and use of AI systems that do not perpetuate harmful stereotypes or prejudices.

A short legal perspective on fairness

Discussions on fairness, bias and equality are not exclusive to AI ethics. Law represents another modality of regulation of societal behaviour that shall be briefly mentioned in relation to AI fairness. Furthermore, AI shall respect legal obligations as part of their trustworthiness.

In terms of fairness and regulation, the focus shall be on the anti-discriminatory law that forms an integral part of the legal system of the European Union (EU) and Slovakia. Discrimination defines a situation where an individual is disadvantaged in some way on the basis of one or multiple protected grounds (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018). According to the Article 21 Charter of the fundamental rights of the EU: "Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, color, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited." This provision is further supplemented by the EU secondary legislation implemented in the EU member states laws³.

³ Namely Racial Equality Directive (2000/43/EC); Employment Equality Directive (2000/78/EC); Gender Equality Directive (recast) (2006/54/EC); Gender Access Directive (2004/113/EC).

Discrimination according to the EU law has two forms – direct and indirect discrimination. Direct discrimination is when a person is treated less favorably on the basis of protected grounds (including discrimination by association). Indirect discrimination: occurs when an apparently neutral rule disadvantages a person or a group sharing the same characteristics (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe, 2018). These concepts are interpreted by courts in specific litigations.

However, EU non-discriminatory law is highly contextual and cases are decided on a case-by-case basis by courts taking into account various factors related to culture, environment, society, and policy. This means that it is challenging to “automate fairness” from the point of the regulation (Wachter et. al., 2021).

Additionally, requirements for mitigation of biases are reflected in the proposal for the EU Artificial Intelligence Act. According to the proposal providers of high-risk AI systems shall examine training, validation and testing data in view of possible biases. What is more, datasets used in high-risk AI systems shall also be representative. The final wording of aforementioned obligations is still subject to discussion on the level of the legislative process.

AI, fairness, and gender gap

In the field of AI ensuring fairness is of paramount importance, and this crucial aspect is at the core of AI ethics, a sub-discipline of applied ethics. Hallamaa and Kalliokoski (2022) propose a pragmatic perspective, suggesting that instead of becoming entangled in the intricate definitions of moral principles and lofty ideals, AI ethics should prioritize scrutinizing how AI influences the real world. This shift in focus has the potential to make AI ethics more tangible and relevant in practical terms. By concentrating on the methodologies that drive tangible changes in the real world, AI ethics can actively contribute to enhancing the design and development of AI technologies, ultimately leading to a more practical influence on ethical considerations.

It is important to emphasize, however, that AI ethics should not overlook the societal impact and biases affecting the development and governance of AI systems. These aspects deserve careful attention.

Focus on addressing algorithmic biases may manifest as two significant concerns: *representational harm* and *allocation harm* (Stanczak & Augenstein, 2021). Representational harm arises when AI unfairly portrays certain groups, reinforcing stereotypes. Allocation harm occurs when AI generates unjust disparities in opportunities and resources. Reducing such biases is intricately connected to the efforts aimed at addressing gender disparities in society.

Representational harm is a concept that focuses on how certain groups are unfairly depicted or portrayed. It involves the negative or biased representations of these groups, which can lead to various forms of harm and reinforce stereotypes and prejudices. Representational harms encompass a range of biased behaviors and consequences that algorithms and systems can exhibit (Stanczak & Augenstein, 2021). For example, when a system translates a sentence such as "The doctor is skilled; she is very knowledgeable" from a language with gendered pronouns to one without such pronouns, the translation system may assign a default gender to the word "doctor" based on stereotypes. If the default is male, it reinforces the stereotype that doctors are typically men.

Allocation harm refers to the unfair distribution of opportunities and resources that occurs as a result of algorithmic interventions. This type of harm can lead to systematic disparities in how individuals and groups are treated, potentially resulting in the denial of specific services or the exclusion of particular groups. This can have significant social, economic, and ethical implications by perpetuating inequalities and biases (Stanczak & Augenstein, 2021). For example, if a translation system consistently assigns gendered adjectives or pronouns to job descriptions, it can influence how job postings are perceived. If technical roles are translated with masculine language and administrative roles with feminine language, it may lead to the exclusion of certain genders from considering or applying for specific jobs, contributing to gender-based employment disparities.

Addressing gender bias in AI is incredibly important because it's all about making AI fair for everyone. It helps ensure that AI systems treat people equally, which is something we all want. It also goes hand in hand with our goal of creating a more fair and just society. By getting rid of bias in AI, we build trust and confidence in these technologies, which is vital. However, fairness is but one puzzle piece when it comes to AI ethics. We need to think of it as one of the important building blocks in making AI trustworthy. There are other crucial aspects, too, such as ensuring AI systems are

easy to understand and explain. This way, we can hold them accountable for their actions and make sure they make sense to everyone.

References

- ALTAI. European Commission. Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology. (2020). [The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence \(ALTAI\) for self assessment.](#)
- Dignum, V. (2021). [The Myth of Complete AI-Fairness](#) (arXiv:2104.12544). arXiv.
- EGTAI. European Commission. Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology. (2019). [Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI.](#)
- European Union (2007). Treaty of Lisbon.
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe (2018). [Handbook on European non-discrimination law.](#) 2018 Edition.
- Hallamaa, J., & Kalliokoski, T. (2022). [AI Ethics as Applied Ethics.](#) Frontiers in Computer Science.
- Schwartz, R., Vassilev, A., Greene, K., Perine, L., Burt, A., & Hall, P. (2022). [Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence.](#) National Institute of Standards and Technology.
- Stanczak, K., & Augenstein, I. (2021). [A Survey on Gender Bias in Natural Language Processing](#) (arXiv:2112.14168). arXiv.
- Wachter, Sandra et. al. (2021). [Why fairness cannot be automated: Bridging the gap between EU non-discrimination law and AI.](#) In Computer Law & Security Review, Volume 41, July 2021, 105567

4. Gender Stereotypes

Stereotypes can be broadly characterized as fixed patterns of thinking people have about themselves and others, or “*over-generalized beliefs about people based on their membership in one of many social categories*” (EIGE, 2013). These categories might exist along with characteristics such as sex, gender identity, race and ethnicity, nationality, age, socioeconomic status, language, and so forth. Several studies show that stereotypes tend to be directed especially at the groups having a subordinate position in the society such as ethnic minorities or women (Talbot, 2003). To “stereotype someone” means to interpret their behavior, personality, and so on in terms of a set of common-sense attributions that are applied to the whole groups (Cameron & Coates, 1988 cited in Talbot, 2003, p. 468) – for example, Slovaks are religious and traditional or Roma people are good at arts. People do not only have stereotypes about members of other groups (heterostereotypes), they also have stereotypes about themselves and the social groups they belong to (autostereotypes) (Sociologický ústav ČAV, 2023).

Stereotypes are the subject of research in various disciplines, especially in social psychology and sociology which define them either more narrowly as cognitive and thought structures or more broadly as extending mental patterns with established patterns of behavior and action. For example, the American Psychological Association defines stereotypes as “*a set of cognitive generalizations (e.g., beliefs, expectations) about the qualities and characteristics of the members of a group or social category. Stereotypes, like schemas, simplify and expedite perceptions and judgments, but they are often exaggerated, negative rather than positive, and resistant to revision even when perceivers encounter individuals with qualities that do not fit the stereotype*” (APA, 2023).

The effect of stereotypes does not always have to be negative. By simplifying the perceived reality they can help individuals in the process of adaptation to the social conditions and rules of the society. On the other hand, precisely because they are simplistic and generalizing and because they attribute certain characteristics to all members of a given social group, they prevent us from perceiving and evaluating people in their uniqueness. Additionally, they are characterized not only by a simplistic interpretation of social phenomena but also by emotionality and

irrationality in that they often do not reflect reality – that is why they are frequently used in propaganda (Petrušek et al., 1996).

Gender stereotypes, as a specific category of stereotypes, can be understood as simplified images of “masculinity” and “femininity”. They are “*relatively fixed, overly simplified concepts of the attitudes and behaviors considered normal and appropriate for a male or female in a particular culture. Gender stereotypes often support the social conditioning of gender roles*” (APA, 2023). Gender stereotypes are formed on the basis of assigning some set of qualities, activities, and ways of behaving to women on one side and to men on the other (for example, a man is active, independent, proactive, uncompromising, decisive, strong, while a woman is passive, patient, caring, self-sacrificing, gentle, faithful). Through the process of socialization, they are reproduced and passed from generation to generation as certain cultural codes. Stereotypes are considerably reductionist, “like caricatures, they focus obsessively on certain characteristics, real or imagined, and exaggerate them” (Talbot, 2003, p. 468). As they accompany us in all areas of life and reproduce immediately, they construct an *appearance of naturalness* (Kiczková, 2011).

Gender stereotypes vs. gender roles

Gender stereotypes are closely related to *gender roles*. Gender roles are social roles that are prescribed to men and women by social and cultural norms existing in a given society and historical situation. They constitute a part of more general social norms linking them to gender differences and ideals of femininity and masculinity, accepted and assumed in the particular society (Aspekt, 2006). Gender roles are associated with a set of expectations and rules related to the idea of masculinity and femininity. They are mostly unwritten and informal, determined by the given society, and define the behavior, way of thinking, feeling, clothing, or form of partner relationships that is suitable/inappropriate for women and men. As stereotypes, gender roles are adopted and reproduced through the process of socialization.

The line between “gender role” and “gender stereotype” is not clear-cut. According to Eagly's theory of social roles, gender roles are produced by the gendered division of labor and societal expectations based on stereotypes. Behavior is strongly influenced by gender roles when cultures approve of gender stereotypes and have explicit expectations based on those stereotypes. At the same time, the very division of

women and men into different social roles is a source of gender stereotyping (Eagly & Steffen, 1984).

Eagly refers to **communal and agentic dimensions of gender-stereotyped characteristics**. The communal role is characterized by attributes such as raising children and showing emotions, which are commonly associated with women. The agentic role is synonymous with being assertive and independent, commonly associated with public activities, and thus with men. In other words, qualities stereotypically attributed to women, such as emotionality, care, empathy, or sacrifice are suitable for fulfilling the traditional gender role of women within the private sphere of the family and especially for raising children. Qualities stereotypically attributed to men, such as activity, assertiveness, rationality, competitiveness, or willingness to take risks are desirable in the public sphere of employment, politics, business, etc.

How stereotypes are structured

As already indicated, gender stereotypes do not only describe what women and men are like, but also set expectations for what they should be like. This means that, in addition to the *descriptive component*, they also contain a normative component and fulfill a normative role. The prescriptive character of gender stereotypes refers to the normative power of gender (pre-)conception. Indeed, people (women and men) behave and act, knowing they are evaluated based on (normative) conceptions of what is regarded as appropriate for their sex (EIGE, 2013). In case the person does not meet the expectations prescribed by the norm, the sanction usually follows, even if only in the form of social condemnation or ridicule.

Let us consider an example of a gender stereotyping statement, according to which women prefer family care to a scientific career. This statement may appear as an empirical fact, as a description of the reality in the field of science where women are less represented in higher positions or career ranks. However, this statement does not only describe an empirical fact (lower representation of women) but also explains it by linking it to the (presumed) difference in the value orientation of women (prioritizing childcare over a professional career). At the same time, it establishes this preference as a norm, which becomes obvious if we notice how women who do not comply with it are often negatively evaluated as “careerist”, which is characteristic with a negative connotation.

Gender stereotypes use “*bipolarization*”, meaning that characteristics attributed to women are in stark contrast to those attributed to men (passive-active, weak-strong, dependent-independent). Boundaries between those polarities are rather impassable with “either-or” logic being applied (either the person is passive or active). Finally, relations between polarities are asymmetric: higher values are given to the qualities attributed to men than to those attributed to women (passivity is negatively connoted, while activity is positively connoted).

Gender stereotypes are also characterized by *simplification*, *reductionism*, and *naturalization* (Talbot, 2003). By sorting human characteristics, abilities, and behaviors into two mutually exclusive categories, gender stereotypes significantly flatten and distort our perceptions of femininity and masculinity, as well as our perceptions of what real women and men are like. At the same time, by implicitly hierarchizing male characteristics over feminine ones, they contribute to the persistence and reproduction of gender inequalities (Kiczková, 2011).

Do stereotypes change over time?

Some stereotypes have a flexible nature, they easily “adapt” to social changes and expectations. On the other hand, there are stereotypes that have a more rigid character and persist even if the social conditions in which they were formed change. Stereotypes about what a “proper” man or a “proper” woman should be – or simply gender stereotypes are an example of such persistent stereotypes.

Gender stereotypes have considerable inertia and change only very slowly. In conjunction with the gender division of labor, they exist across all cultures (Eagly, Beall & Sternberg 2005). Recent studies show that even though gender stereotypes have a dynamic character, they change over time and space more slowly than gender roles. Although the female gender role is no longer defined as a domestic role in social reality, women are still stereotypically attributed to the characteristics associated with the role of a housewife and child raiser. One explanation for why some stereotypical gender perceptions have not changed fundamentally despite societal changes has been that some stereotypes persist in acting as a barrier against the uncertainties of new gender roles (EIGE, 2013).

Similarly, the **association between gender and personality traits** typically perceived as female (emotionality, warmth and kindness, interest in children, sensitiveness,

patience, tenderness) on the one hand and traits typically perceived as male on the other (assertiveness, activity, competitiveness, independence, self-confidence, business-mindedness, ambitiousness, decisiveness, capability of leadership, rationality, aggressiveness and willingness to take risks) is remarkably consistent over time, geographically and across age and sex groups.

Although explicitly negative gender stereotypes are currently less accepted, implicit, unreflected gender stereotypes and prejudices persist and are identifiable in various spheres. They have a significant, but little obvious influence on consciousness (Petrušek et al., 1996, p. 1230). For example, in science, research, and technology, the (often unreflected) association of science and the scientific profession with masculinity still persists.

Impact of stereotypes

Gender stereotypes contribute to the reproduction of unequal social relations between women and men and in this sense, they have negative consequences that can be manifested both on the individual and societal level. Stereotypes, or stereotyping, contributes to the maintenance of the social and symbolic order; both involve a strategy of “splitting”, whereby the normal and acceptable are separated from the abnormal and unacceptable, resulting in the exclusion of the latter (Talbot, 2003).

Gender stereotypes hold individual men and women within boundaries limiting their possibilities of free self-realization and preventing them from pursuing their individual interests and abilities. Individualization of life projects is not possible without loosening these boundaries (Kiczková, 2011). If, for example, we understand politics or business as a “tough game”, we implicitly assume that self-assertive people will succeed in them, and we stereotypically attribute these qualities to men. Women are considered not equipped for careers in politics. On the other hand, the stereotype of a woman as an emotional and empathetic caregiver is linked with parenthood often being limited to motherhood, or motherhood being considered the only “real” parenthood. The father's role is reduced to a “supervising” role, or to “entertaining kids” and “giving life advice”.

On a personal level, we can also talk about the so-called *stereotype threat* (Steele, 1997): when the person is reminded of their belonging to the stereotyped group their

performance is affected so that it is consistent with the stereotype (Crasnow, 2009). For example, if girls are reminded that they are girls they perform worse in mathematics tests when the dominant stereotype is that “girls don't do math”.

At the societal level, gender stereotypes undoubtedly play a role in various forms of disadvantaging women across different areas of life including the labor market (including the gender pay gap), science, and politics. They also contribute to the perpetuation of violence against women (the stereotype of a strong man and the head of the family).

Gender stereotypes are also a source of *gender bias* describing a variety of stereotypical beliefs about individuals based on their sex and leading to differential treatment of women and men (EIGE, 2013). Often the bias is implicit – unintentional and automatic stemming from traditions, norms, values, culture, and/or experience. Automatic associations feed into decision-making, enabling a quick assessment of an individual according to gender and gender stereotypes (ILO, 2017). Gender bias, even in its implicit form can have a significant impact on our real-life decisions. It affects how girls and boys choose a major for their university studies, how employers select and promote their employees, or how society treats its vulnerable groups.

Gender stereotypes in language

Language as a system of representations and the tool for communication and thinking is closely linked with gender relations; therefore, it has been in focus of gender and feminist research since the 1970s. Gender stereotypes as mental images of femininity and masculinity are most often manifested in language either at the level of formal structure (grammar)⁴ or at the level of language use. Within feminist linguistics, three basic forms of disadvantaging women in language can be distinguished (Ostertágová, 2014):

- **Making women invisible in the language:** for example, through the use of *generic masculine* meaning that plural of the masculine form is used to denote groups in which there are both women and men, while the singular forms are used to denote general names – professions or job positions.

⁴ Gender is reflected in the grammatical structure of languages to a different extent. For example, there are languages that do not have grammatical gender (such as Hungarian) or languages where the gender is only reflected in pronouns (e.g., English). Most Slavic languages have strongly gendered grammar structures meaning that words, including verbs, adjectives, nouns, and even numbers, change and transform based on gender – plural or singular – and the case.

- **Distinctive definition of women in language:** for example, the change of a surname after marriage symbolically determining the dependence of women's individuality on a man; using the terms "miss" and "missis"; using the feminine form to denote the whole group based on the assumption that all members of a category, such as a profession, share a gender – e.g., talking about "učiteľky" (female teachers in Slovak) to describe all teachers (EIGE, 2023).
- **Understating women:** masculinity is mostly associated by terms with positive connotations, such as strength, dominance, and assertiveness, while femininity is mostly associated with negatively connoted terms, such as weakness, submissiveness, or passivity (for example, "*bud' chlap*" – "be a man, have courage" vs. "*nebud' baba*" – "don't be a sissy")

Even in its very subtle form, the gendered use of a language may have an adverse effect in certain social situations. For example, several studies demonstrated that when the generic masculine is used in job adverts, women tend to respond with a less expected identification with the job (Stout & Dasgupta, 2011). But even when the job descriptions use gender-inclusive language, gender preferences can still be conveyed with more subtle cues such as traits and stereotypes typically associated with certain genders. For example, including gendered words such as *competitive*, *dominant*, or *leader* associated with male stereotypes in job advertisements could make the position seem less appealing to women (Gaucher, Friesen, & Key, 2011).

Gender stereotypes and prejudices anchored in language are currently attracting attention in connection with the progress in developing AI and machine learning since they are embedded in text sources and result in machine learning algorithms learning stereotypical concepts of gender (Leavy, 2018). Gender prejudices are present in texts in various forms, e.g., using the generic masculine when naming groups of people, naming the male first when both genders are mentioned (e.g., son and daughter, husband and wife) as well as in descriptions of persons.

We also find gender stereotypes in connection with women and men as language users expressing their ideas in different styles of speech or communication. Stereotypically problem-solving, reporting, lecturing, public, status, oppositionality, and independence are attributed to the male style, while sympathy, rapport, listening, privacy, and connection are attributed to the female style. That is one of the possible explanations for why digital assistants mostly used to have female voices with male options being added only after receiving criticism (LaFrance, 2016).

However, as D. Cameron shows, while in the earlier stages of gender and language research, the opinion according to which women's characteristic way of speaking was, indeed, a factor making women unsuitable candidates for positions of public authority and responsibility, currently the opposite concept is coming to the fore, according to which "women are superior language users". *"Today, by contrast, women are regularly represented as model language users: their verbal skills are seen, moreover, as central to what is portrayed as the fulfillment of that old prophecy 'the future is female'."* (Cameron, 2014).

Gender stereotypes and Slovakia

As we noted, gender stereotypes are persistent over time and space. However, there are considerable differences in how they are demonstrated in gender roles across cultures with some countries still leaning towards a traditional division of gender roles, while in other countries gender roles become more varied. The traditional division of gender roles assigns the role of breadwinner to the man and the role of taking care of the household to the woman. In advanced post-industrial societies, both women and men can assume both roles without compromising their dignity.

Compared to countries in Western or Northern Europe, the perception of the division of gender roles remains rather traditionalist in Slovakia, especially with regard to the role of women as first and foremost a mother. According to the results of the European Values Survey (Strancová & Zeman, 2019)⁵, 67% of Slovak women agree with the statement that a woman must have children to have a fulfilling life, with more women than men agreeing with the statement. More than 70% of the population agrees that *"employment is a good thing, but most women still want to have their own household and children"*. 38.2% of Slovaks agree that family life suffers if a woman works. On the other hand, more than 46% of respondents agreed that men are better than women at managing companies. At the same time, almost 30% of respondents think that higher education is more important for men than for women (Halman, Reeskens, Sieben, & van Zunder, 2022), even though there have been more women than men among university students in Slovakia for almost a

⁵ A useful source of information about stereotypes and their dynamics or persistence in time and space is offered, for example, by international research focused on values such as Research of European values or World value survey. These surveys include the same set of questions for all countries and are repeated over time, thus making it possible to monitor the dynamics of the development of values and their variability in different cultures.

decade. In this specific question, the Slovak population also differs significantly from its neighbors in the region, where such an opinion is much less common.

Similar results can also be observed in the Eurobarometer survey from 2017 (European Commission, 2017) focusing on perceptions of gender equality and the prevalence of stereotypical beliefs. According to the survey, a quarter of Slovaks think that it is not acceptable for men to cry, while on average only one in ten European Union (EU) citizens thinks so. 73% of Slovaks believe that the most important role of a woman is to take care of her home and family, and 75% of Slovaks consider earning money to be the most important role of men. It needs to be mentioned that similar perceptions are widely shared in most post-communist countries. On the other hand, only 11% and 10% of the population in Sweden share similar views, respectively – the country with the least stereotypical view of gender roles in the whole EU.

This regional division is also visible in the Eurobarometer *gender stereotype index* providing a broader overview of the tendency to accept the gender stereotypes presented. Slovakia ranked among the countries with the highest value of the index⁶.

Figure 3.1: Gender stereotype index across the EU (European Commission, 2017). The index indicates how strong stereotypical views are in each country.

Stereotypical views also persist in how Slovaks perceive women's participation in politics with women being seen as more emotional, less ambitious, and not being tough enough for politics. Up to 60% of Slovaks think women are less ambitious than men, and this proportion is the highest in the EU. At the same time, Slovak men and

⁶ The index is composed of an average value based on the answers to the set of five questions asked to measure the tendency to accept the gender stereotypes presented. The higher the value of the indicator, the higher the acceptance of gender stereotypes.

women do not perceive the way women are presented in the media as problematic. 48% think that such a problem does not exist and 18% think it exists but does not need to be solved. As in the case of general stereotypes, Slovakia belongs among the countries with the most stereotypical view of the political participation of women in the EU (European Commission, 2017).

These stereotypical views did not change much after the first female president was elected in 2019 as a survey from 2020 (Bútorová & Gyárfášová, 2020) shows. When asked whether men have better chances in politics, up to 38% of women answered they think men have better chances, and it is right so or right in some way. Almost 70% of respondents – both women and men – thought that men are more rational, tougher, more assertive, and have more authority and better leadership qualities. These stereotypical views are then reflected in the political reality with women hesitant to enter politics and political parties not conscious enough about the need to increase the share of women on their candidate lists resulting in the composition of the national parliament with a very low share of women (less than 22% in 2023).

While overall the stereotypical views still have a strong impact on how men and women are perceived in different areas of life in Slovakia, smaller micro-level studies focusing on specific topics provide examples of how complex and dynamic the effect of stereotypes can be. For example, a study by Adamus (Adamus & Ballová Mikušková, 2023) exploring whether women and men are at risk of differential treatment by Slovak HR professionals in recruitment and dismissal suggests that stereotypical gender perceptions do not impact negatively only women but also men not behaving in masculine and career-oriented way. Findings of the study by Žuffová (Žuffová, 2023) analyzing media coverage of leading presidential candidates in 2019 suggest that when the corruption perception is high and public trust in institutions is low, communal traits (e.g., emotionality, care, empathy, sacrifice) stereotypically attributed to women were appreciated instead of being a disadvantage in the political competition. Finally, a study (Adamus, Čavojová, & Šrol, 2021) investigating how the congruence between the image of a successful entrepreneur and one's own gender-role orientation affects entrepreneurial intentions suggests that while successful entrepreneurs are still perceived as masculine it is not biological sex predicting entrepreneurial intention. Rather, this intention is associated with the extent to which participants felt they resembled successful entrepreneurs, meaning how much they identified with the characteristics perceived as masculine.

References

- Adamus, M., & Ballová Mikušková, E. (2023). [Gender discrimination and the backlash effect in recruitment and dismissal processes: experimental evidence from Slovakia](#). *Gender in Management*.
- Adamus, M., Čavojová, M., & Šrol, J. (2021). [The impact of stereotyped perceptions of entrepreneurship and gender-role orientation on Slovak women's entrepreneurial intentions](#). *Gender in Management*, 36(6), 745-761.
- APA. (2023). *APA Dictionary of Psychology*: [Stereotype](#). Retrieved July 15, 2023.
- Aspekt. (2006). [Glosár rodovej terminológie](#). Retrieved July 5, 2023.
- Bútorová, Z., & Gyárfášová, O. (2020). [Politická participácia žien na Slovensku 2020. Kde sme, kam smerujeme?](#) IVO. Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- Cameron, D. (2014). Gender and Language Ideologies. In S. Ehrlich, M. Meyerhoff, & J. Holmes, *The Handbook of Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. New Jersey: Wiley.
- Cameron, D., & Coates, J. (2003). Women in Their Speech Communities. In M. Talbot, *Gender stereotypes: reproduction and challenge (in The Handbook of Language and Gender)* (p. 468). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Crasnow, S. (2009). Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. In Edward N. Zalta & Uri Nodelman (eds.), [The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy \(Fall 2023 Edition\): Feminist Perspectives on Science](#). Retrieved July 15, 2023.
- Eagly, A., & Steffen, V. (1984). Gender Stereotypes Stem From the Distribution of Women and Men Into Social Roles. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 46(4), 735 – 754.
- Eagly, A. H., Beall, A. E., & Sternberg, R. J. (Eds.). (2005). *The psychology of gender*. Guilford Press.
- EIGE. (2013). [A Study of Collected Narratives on Gender Perceptions in the 27 EU Member States](#). Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- EIGE. (2023). [Gender Sensitive Communication](#). Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- European Commission. (2017). [Gender equality and gender pay gap](#). *Special Eurobarometer*. Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- Gaucher, D., Friesen, D., & Key, A. (2011). Evidence That Gendered Wording in Job Advertisements Exists and Sustains Gender Inequality. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 101(1), 109-128.
- Halman, N., Reeskens, T., Sieben, I., & van Zunder, M. (2022). *Atlas of European Values: Change and Continuity in Turbulent Times*. Tilburg University.
- ILO. (2017). [Breaking barriers: Unconscious gender bias in the workplace](#). Retrieved July 15, 2023.
- Kiczková, Z. (2011). Moc rodových stereotypov. In Z. & Kiczková, *Rodové štúdiá. Súčasná diskusia, problémy a perspektívy*. (pp. 122-145). Bratislava: Univerzita Komenského.

LaFrance, A. (2016). [Why do so many digital assistants have feminine names? Hey Cortana. Hey Siri. Hey girl.](#) *The Atlantic*. Retrieved July 30, 2023.

Leavy, S. S. (2018). Gender bias in artificial intelligence: the need for diversity and gender theory in machine learning. *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Gender Equality in Software Engineering (GE '18)*. Association for Computing.

Ostertágová, A. (2014). Vybrané psychologické aspekty rodovo a/symetrického jazyka v sociolingvistickej kontexte. In J. Cviková et al., *Analýza významu a možností používania rodovo vyváženého jazyka*. (pp. 47-75). Bratislava: Centrum vzdelávania MPSVR SR.

Petrusek, M. et al. (1996). *Veľký sociologický slovník II*. Praha: Karolinum.

Sociologický ústav ČAV. (2023). [Sociologická encyklopédia: Stereotyp](#). Retrieved July 15, 2023.

Steele, C. M. (1997). [A threat in the air: How stereotypes shape intellectual identity and performance.](#) *American Psychologist*, 613–629.

Stout, J., & Dasgupta, N. (2011). [When he doesn't mean you: Gender-exclusive language as ostracism.](#) *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 37(6), 757-769.

Strancová, K., & Zeman, M. (2019). [Výskum európskych hodnôt 2017 – Slovensko. Pramenná publikácia](#), Bratislava: Sociologický ústav SAV. Retrieved August 15, 2023.

Talbot, M. (2003). Gender stereotypes: reproduction and challenge. In J. Holmes, & M. Meyerhoff, *The Handbook of Language and Gender* (pp. 468-486). Blackwell: Oxford.

Žuffová, M. (2023). [Gender stereotypes in print and online media coverage of Slovak presidential candidates in 2009 and 2019.](#) *European Political Science Review*, 75-95.

5. Evaluation of Slovak AI Systems

The overall goal of our project was to detect various forms of gender bias within Slovak AI systems. This chapter describes the experimental evaluation we have performed. As such, the AI models of today are very complex beasts based on *deep learning* technology. It is not entirely easy to understand how these models work or how to describe their behavior. For this reason, their evaluation must be performed as an empirical experiment. We carefully prepare inputs for these systems and define how a biased or unbiased AI system would work with these inputs. We then observe the actual behavior of the systems and compare the behavior with the expectations.

In the rest of this chapter, we first describe how we assembled a list of common gender stereotypes serving as the starting point for our attempts to understand the stereotypization occurring in AI systems. We will then describe how we use this list of stereotypes to measure the degree to which the machine translation systems use the stereotypes to select either *masculine* or *feminine* gender when translating text from English to Slovak. We perform similar experiments with *masked language models* as well. Finally, we will describe how we evaluated the performance gap in how speech-to-text models handle male and female voices.

List of stereotypes

To understand how much AI systems rely on stereotypes, we must first define the exact list of stereotypes we would like to study. In our project, we have identified 7 stereotypes about women and 9 stereotypes about men that form the theoretical starting point for our experiments. We have based the definition of the list of stereotypes on existing work from gender theory, mostly based on the work by the *European Institute for Gender Equality* (EIGE, 2013) and *Valdřová (2018)*. We have collected a list of more than 100 common stereotypes about both men and women. Then we have distilled this list into 16 broader categories based on our perception of what these stereotypes have in common and we let gender experts from Slovakia validate this list and provide feedback that was then incorporated. Even though this list is mainly meant to serve as a list of gender stereotypes for Slovak culture, we believe that it can also very well serve broader European or Western culture as well.

Note that this list includes stereotypes that can be considered both positive (e.g., *men are professional*) and negative (e.g., *women are irrational*). The stereotypes, by

design, can also be inherently illogical and contradictory. For example, men are both *childish* and *rational*. The stereotypes are both about what is believed to be true about the genders, but also about the beliefs about what a “proper” man or a “proper” woman *should* be like.

Our list of gender stereotypes

1. Women are **emotional and irrational**
2. Women are **gentle, kind and submissive**
3. Women are **empathetic and caring**
4. Women are **neat and diligent**
5. Women are **social**
6. Women are **weak**
7. Women are **beautiful**
8. Men are **tough and rough**
9. Men are **self-confident**
10. Men are **professional**
11. Men are **rational**
12. Men are **breadwinners**
13. Men are **leaders**
14. Men are **childish**
15. Men are **strong**
16. Men are **sexual**

Machine translation

Machine translation is an immensely popular application of AI. People use tools such as *Google Translate* or *DeepL* in their everyday lives, but the same tools are also often used in business environments. Here, we study the gender biases present in English-to-Slovak translation systems.

For the purposes of this project, we focus on the fact that there are many cases when English sentences do not have an indication of *grammatical gender*, while the corresponding Slovak sentences have it. For example, the following English sentence is gender-neutral, while the Slovak translation needs to select a specific gender for the first person:

[EN] *I am emotional*

[SK] Masculine: *Som emotívny*

[SK] Feminine: *Som emotívna*

When the translation is taking place, the machine translation system must make the decision about the gender for the adjective *emotional*. We study the generated translations of machine translation systems to understand the way they make their decisions. We focus on two particular types of gender bias that English-to-Slovak machine translation systems can have. It should be noted that other types of bias also exist but were left out for the purposes of this project.

The two types of gender bias we aim to study in machine translation systems

1. Stereotypical gender assignment

Do systems assign gender in a way that agrees with generally accepted stereotypes about genders? It is possible that the samples used for training machine translation systems are gendered stereotypically and the AI models have learned this. For example, a machine translation system with stereotypical reasoning would translate *I am emotional* with the feminine gender, and *I am rational* with the masculine gender.

Models that use stereotypical decision-making reinforce existing stereotypes. This might make the system less usable for individual users, but it can also be problematic if the outputs of such a system are used in *downstream* applications, as they can reinforce the stereotypes in them.

2. *Male as norm* behavior

It is often the case that most of the texts present on the Web are written by men from a male perspective. Data used to train machine translation models can be similar and machine translation systems can *by default* translate everything into the *masculine* gender. This makes the system less usable for people who would prefer to have the texts written from a *female* point of view.

Data collection

To create a dataset that would test these biases, we have hired English-Slovak translators to create English sentences that we can use. These sentences have to fulfill several criteria:

- The sentence must be gender-neutral in the English language.
- During the English-to-Slovak translation, the machine translation system has to select one of the two genders.
- The gender selection should be associated with a specific stereotype from our list of 16 stereotypes.

The example above (“*I am emotional*”) is one such sentence. It is gender-neutral in English, but after translation to Slovak, gender must be assigned to the adjective *emotional*. At the same time, this selection suggests how a machine translation system behaves when stereotypically female *emotionality* is present in the text.

Together we have collected 4,002 such samples. Each of the 5 data creators has created 50 samples for each of the 16 stereotypes. After the collection was done, members of our team validated the samples to ensure the quality of the data. This was a vetoing process where the validators made sure that the sentences were indeed representative of the particular stereotype. This process has removed 321 samples.

Subjectivity of stereotypes

A limitation of this data collection process is the fact that stereotypes are often subjective and different people might perceive them in different ways. A sentence that one person considers stereotypical might be considered harmless by others. The personal views have influenced both data creation and data validation and as such, the resulting dataset inherently reflects the beliefs of the people involved.

Data translation

We used 4 machine translation systems – *Amazon Translate*, *ChatGPT*, *DeepL*, and *Google Translate* – to translate all the validated English samples to Slovak⁷. Apart from *ChatGPT*, the other three systems are commercial machine translation systems with *Google Translate* being the most popular translation system in Slovakia. *ChatGPT*, on the other hand, is a general chatbot language model that is able to respond to arbitrary requests. To make it work as a translator, we asked it to translate texts from English to Slovak. Despite the fact that it was not explicitly trained to perform any machine translation, it is able to generate translations, although its performance still lags behind specialized systems.

We are interested in what gender these systems selected for individual examples. To do so, we have used several grammatical rules and heuristics to automatically detect the gender of the translations:

- We performed syntactic analysis (*dependency parsing* and *part-of-speech tagging*) of the translated sentences using the *Trankit* model for the Slovak language. We observe the predicted grammatical gender of the verbs and adjectives that are *heads* of the first person word *som* ([EN] *am* or *was*).
- We searched for the gendered words *rád/rada* ([EN] *to like*) and *sám/sama* ([EN] *self* or *myself*).
- We force the systems to produce *masculine* and *feminine* variants of the sentence by *prompting*. We have added a prefix “*The man said:*” or “*The woman said:*” before the sentence. This should indicate to the model the gender of the first person. Note that this process is not perfect and some models produced translations with an incorrect gender. We counted the number of gendered adjectives and verbs in these gendered variants and compared them with the default translation.

⁷ All the machine translation systems were queried in August 2023.

With these methods, we were able to automatically assign gender to roughly 90% of the translated sentences. The methods are quite precise and when they predict that the sentence is *masculine* or *feminine*, they have almost 100% accuracy. We checked 100 randomly selected samples for these two cases and we have not found a single misclassified example. Our method does not assign any gender for roughly 10% of the cases. From these, roughly two thirds are indeed genderless by our estimates.

Results

Below we show the results for the 16 stereotypes for the 4 machine translation systems we evaluated. For each stereotype, we calculated the confidence interval ($\alpha = 0.95$) for the percentage of how often the system selects the *masculine* gender during the translation. The pink intervals show the female stereotypes and the blue intervals show the male stereotypes. The dashed vertical lines show the overall rate for either *masculine* or *feminine* stereotypes.

Figure 5.2: Percentage of translations that have the **masculine gender**. Pink and blue indicate stereotypes about women and men, respectively. The dashed lines show the average percentage across female and male stereotypes.

All the systems exhibit both biases we mentioned. *Male as norm* behavior is shown by the fact that we have a higher than 50% rate of *masculine* translations for almost all the stereotypes. Models exhibiting stereotypical behavior is shown by the fact that the stereotypically male examples have higher rates of *masculine* gender than the stereotypically female examples.

It also seems that these two biases are negatively correlated and they contradict each other. *Amazon Translate* and *ChatGPT* have stronger *male as norm* behavior, but they rarely use stereotypical thinking (in other words, they rarely select the *feminine* gender in general). On the other hand, *Google Translate* and especially *DeepL* are more likely to use the *feminine* gender, but they are also more influenced by stereotypes.

Stereotype #7: "Women are beautiful" seems to be the strongest *feminine* stereotype. The samples are usually related to beauty products, self-care, self-image, and other topics that the machine translation systems strongly associate with women. *Stereotype #15: "Men are sexual"* belongs to the most *feminine* male stereotypes in our dataset, especially in *DeepL*. We believe that this might be caused by how women are portrayed in the training data. The sexualization of women is a common occurrence on the Web and this might have influenced how texts with sexual undertones are translated.

ChatGPT uses gender-neutral punctuation

We have observed that *ChatGPT* will in roughly 10% of the cases use punctuation marks that are sometimes used to make Slovak text gender-neutral. *ChatGPT* knows how to use:

- **Female suffix parentheses:** "*Vedel(a) som to*" ([EN] "*I knew it*"). These are used when the female form of the text has a specific suffix at the end of gendered words, in this case, *-a*.
- **Male and female variants separated with a slash:** "*Som veselý/veselá*" or alternatively "*Som veselý/á*" ([EN] "*I'm happy*"). In the first case both male and female variants of the word are shown, in the second case it is suggested that only the suffix should be considered.

This is an interesting approach that *ChatGPT* probably learned to imitate from the available Web data. Punctuation like this is usually not present in the parallel corpora used to train classical machine translation systems.

Discussion

Our experiments show that both forms of gender bias behavior that we theoretically predicted are indeed present in machine translation systems. The systems will use the *masculine* gender more often, making the systems less usable for users who would like to have a *feminine* gender in their translations. These users have to manually edit the outputs of the system. At the same time, the models *will* use stereotypes to decide the gender of the outputs, and by this, they can contribute to the reinforcement of the existing stereotypes.

A natural question might arise: How should we address these biases? We measure the percentage of the *masculine* and *feminine* translations, so it might seem that a theoretically optimal unbiased model would have an equal probability of generating one or the other. This would seemingly address the issues of fairness, but the resulting system might be frustrating for the users, as they would have to check the grammar in all their texts to make it consistent. In our opinion, **a proper solution would be to give users options to control the text generation process**, as was done in some languages in *Google Translate* (e.g., for Spanish).

These changes would require the operators of these machine translation systems to invest in the efforts to create such a new feature in their products. We hope that the data we have collected and that we plan to release will make this easier in the future, providing the operators with tools to measure and test the behavior of their systems.

Language models

Language models are one of the most important technologies of current AI, as they are used to *power* a plethora of AI systems, including popular chatbots such as *ChatGPT*. Language models are first created by the so-called *pre-training*, when they learn about languages from vast Internet-based text corpora, and they obtain various linguistic skills. Then, they are *fine-tuned* to employ these linguistic skills for various applications, such as *text analysis*, *machine translation*, *chatting*, and many others. In fact, they are used in most natural language processing applications today and there are millions of these models already deployed.

As such, language models are often not directly used by the users (in a way machine translation systems can be used). Instead, their role is often to be the backbone for *downstream* AI systems that are then used by the users or that process users' texts

without them even knowing it. Due to their extensive deployment, they are an interesting target for our evaluation, because any bias present in them can in fact manifest itself in these downstream applications as well.

In this work, we study the behavior of *masked language models*. These language models are pre-trained to perform the so-called *word filling*: They try to predict a word that is masked in an input text. For example, this is one such case:

Masked English sentence: *I always <?> kids.*

Desired token: *wanted*

The model is expected to guess that the token that was in the sentence before masking was the word *wanted*. We can study how the model handles grammatical gender in the Slovak language:

English sentence: *I always <?> kids.*

Slovak sentence: *Vždy som <?> deti.*

Masculine token: *chcel*

Feminine token: *chcela*

The decision process here can have the same two types of gender bias as the machine translation systems had in the previous section. Note that, by itself, this behavior is probably not particularly problematic or harmful. Not many users interact with the masked language models in this way – most people do not need an AI system that is able to predict a masked word. The reason to study the gender biases in these models is the hypothesis that the gender bias measured here will transfer to the *downstream* applications that use these models as backbones.

There are good reasons to assume that gender biases indeed exist within language models, as they are usually created from the vast Web-based text corpora and the data might thus contain many texts with stereotypical opinions. The texts are also mostly written in the *masculine* gender by male authors.

The two types of gender bias we aim to study in masked language models

1. Stereotypical gender assignment

Do language models use stereotypical “thinking” when they have to decide the grammatical gender of a word that needs to be filled in? The stereotypical behavior might transfer to downstream applications and these stereotypes could influence how the deployed systems process texts or how they respond to the users. These stereotypes can harm certain groups of people if they manifest themselves in sensitive applications, such as hate speech detection, curriculum vitae analysis, and others. For example, a stereotypical language model would give higher probability to the female word *chcela* in the example above.

2. Male as norm behavior

Do language models prefer the *masculine* gender over the *feminine* by default? This behavior could lead to worse performance or accuracy for the downstream models when they process texts with the *feminine* gender. Something similar is in fact happening in English-to-X machine translation systems where the sentences with *she* pronouns have worse translations than identical sentences with *he* pronouns. Similar effects could also happen in other applications.

Data

We reuse the data from the machine translation experiments to generate pairs of *masculine* and *feminine* versions of the same sentence (e.g., “*Vždy som chcel deti*” and “*Vždy som chcela deti*”). To find such pairs, we checked all the translations that were created with gender-specific prompts (“*The man said*” or “*The woman said*”) and selected those that differ in exactly one word. Further, the morphology of this word must indicate that it could be a gendered word (e.g., *plakal* and *plakala*). In total, we were able to extract 3,649 pairs of sentences that match our criteria (228 pairs per stereotype on average).

Results

Language models calculate probabilities for all the words in their vocabulary when they are asked to perform the *word filling*. For each sample in our dataset, we masked the one word that differed between the two sentences in the pair and compared the probabilities calculated for the *masculine* and the *feminine* words. For example, we compare the probabilities for the words *chcel* and *chcela* calculated as possible fill-ins in the masked sentence “Vždy som <?> deti”. The final score is the difference between their \log_{10} values. The greater the number, the more likely it is for the model to select the *masculine* gender. Negative numbers on the other hand indicate that the model selects the *feminine* gender more often.

Below we show the results for four popular language models. *SlovakBERT* is a purely Slovak language model, while the other models are *multilingual* and are able to handle more than 100 languages. Their level of Slovak understanding can differ. Generally, *SlovakBERT* and *XLM-RoBERTa Large* have the best performance, followed by *XLM-RoBERTa Base*, and finally, *mBERT* is the worst-performing model.

Figure 5.3: The score indicates how much more likely it is for the language model to generate a masculine word. A positive score means that the masculine word has a higher probability than the feminine word. Pink and blue indicate stereotypes about women and men, respectively. The dashed lines show the average percentage across female and male stereotypes.

The behavior of the models differ substantially. All the models apart from *mBERT* show stereotypical thinking. The results suggest that the models will select *masculine* gender for stereotypically male sentences 2x to 3x more often than for stereotypically female sentences. This means that they indeed use their stereotypical knowledge to make decisions.

As for the *male as norm* behavior, *mBERT* prefers the *masculine* gender **strongly** across the board for all the stereotypes. Other models are more balanced. *SlovakBERT* still prefers the *masculine* gender, while *XLM-RoBERTa Base* prefers the *feminine* gender. *XLM-RoBERTa Large* finally seems to be the most balanced.

As for individual stereotypes, *Stereotype #7: "Women are beautiful"* seems to be especially strong, and *Stereotype #15: "Men are sexual"* is the most *feminine* of the male stereotypes. These results are similar to what we have observed in the machine translation experiments.

Discussion

Our experiments show concerning levels for at least one type of gender bias in all the language models. Although a common user would probably not know when they interact with these models, they are in fact quite widespread and AI systems trained on similar models are processing data for billions of people every day. The biases we have measured here can seep through and cause harm, while the developers might not even be conscious of it happening.

We hope that our work will help AI researchers and developers to test and evaluate their systems and take steps to mitigate the potential harms to various groups of people. Having the ability to measure and understand how biased the models are is the first step in this effort. The obligation to reinforce fairness here lies with both the providers of the original raw masked language models that we have tested, and with the developers of the downstream AI systems that are ultimately responsible for deploying them and letting them interact with users' data.

Speech-to-text

Casual and professional users alike may use their voice on their smartphones or computers to perform searches, translations, or write emails or documents. AI-based speech-to-text (speech recognition) models are leveraged for this purpose.

In speech-to-text, we consider gender bias to occur when **a model exhibits higher error rates for a specific gender when transcribing an input audio recording to text** – that is, when a speech-to-text model makes more mistakes for one particular gender (males or females).

We examine whether there is gender bias present in speech recognition for the Slovak language. Gender bias has already been reported for several languages – female speech was found to be better recognized than male speech for the Arabic, English, Dutch, and French languages (Feng et al., 2021).

We identified and examined two publicly available datasets (FLEURS and Common Voice) containing audio recordings and transcriptions in multiple languages, including the Slovak language. We perform speech recognition using several publicly available multilingual speech-to-text models. In the rest of this section, we present an overview of the selected datasets and models, and our results.

Examined datasets and models

The **FLEURS dataset** (Conneau et al., 2023) contains sentences representing readings of Wikipedia articles. Based on our observation of a subset of the recordings, the audio quality is relatively high, without strong background noise or unintelligible parts. We only use the test set of this dataset, since the rest may have been used for training speech-to-text models we evaluate.

The number of male and female transcriptions is fairly balanced (58% male, 42% female). Most transcriptions are only recorded by either of these genders, but not both (58%). Transcriptions recorded by both males and females, which we hereinafter refer to as *filtered* transcriptions, are balanced (647 male, 645 female).

The **Common Voice** dataset (Ardila et al., 2020) is a crowdsourced dataset containing mostly short recordings (approx. 78% of all Slovak recordings are composed of 5 or fewer words). Many audio samples are missing a gender (approx. 50%) or have a gender labeled “Other” (approx. 1.3%), both of which we omit from evaluation. The quality of the recordings varies; some contain background noise, plosives, or artifacts as a result of noise removal.

The Common Voice dataset is significantly imbalanced (83% male transcriptions, 17% female transcriptions). The *filtered* dataset is likewise smaller in volume (21% of transcriptions are recorded by both males and females) and more balanced (1002 male, 836 female transcriptions).

We examined the performance of the following speech-to-text models on the selected datasets:

- *Massively Multilingual Speech* (MMS), version FL102 (1 billion parameters)⁸
- *Whisper*, medium size (0.77 billion parameters)⁹
- *Whisper*, large size (1.55 billion parameters)¹⁰

We use two different sizes of the *Whisper* model to assess whether model size has an impact on gender bias.

Results

To quantify the performance of speech-to-text models and their gender bias, we run speech recognition using the specified models and datasets and calculate *error rates* for both males and females. We quantify the bias via the *word error rate* (WER), which represents the percentage of words incorrectly predicted by a model compared to the expected transcription.

Below we show error rates computed from predicted transcriptions (with confidence intervals at $\alpha = 0.95$). The error rates are reported separately for males and females, and for two cases: (1) when the target language is explicitly specified as Slovak before transcription, and (2) when the target language is *auto*-detected language.

⁸ <https://huggingface.co/facebook/mms-1b-fl102>

⁹ <https://huggingface.co/openai/whisper-medium>

¹⁰ <https://huggingface.co/openai/whisper-large-v2>

Figure 5.4: Word error rates per gender for the examined datasets.

Models consistently yield higher error rates for females, indicating gender bias. The bias is present even if only the filtered transcriptions are considered (recorded by both males and females). The bias is also present regardless of whether the Slovak language is specified explicitly on input or the language is detected automatically.

The gender bias is less significant for the *FLEURS* dataset for all examined scenarios. One possible factor influencing the overall performance and the bias is the audio quality. The *Common Voice* dataset has a greater variety of voices (also in terms of age groups) and considerably more noise in audio recordings.

The figures show results for filtered transcriptions, i.e. transcriptions recorded by both males and females. Using all transcriptions could yield skewed results as some words not spoken by the other gender could be transcribed with fewer errors. Additionally, as a side effect, the filtered subset contains a more balanced number of transcriptions in terms of gender. Nevertheless, we also evaluated the WER for all transcriptions, and the same gender bias was identified.

The larger size of the *Whisper* model exhibits reduced differences in error rates for males and females in the *FLEURS* dataset, i.e. **the gender bias is reduced**. This indicates that the model size may affect the bias. The reduction in the bias with increased model size does not hold for the *Common Voice* dataset.

Discussion

We believe that our results, indicating a bias against female voices, reinforce the need to study biases and employ mitigation techniques when developing speech-to-text models. The presence of bias in speech-to-text systems can create a more frustrating experience for a subpopulation for which these systems perform incorrect predictions more frequently. Based on our experiments for the Slovak language, this holds for females, contrary to other examined languages for which males were disadvantaged (Feng et al., 2021). Admittedly, the differences are often so small (e.g., in the case of the *FLEURS* dataset) that it is not possible to reliably tell how strong this effect really is.

One possible contributor to gender bias is the imbalance of training data in favor of one gender. Specifically, in the case of the Meta MMS model, which was trained on the *FLEURS* dataset, the ratio of male to female training transcriptions for the Slovak language is roughly 2:1. Balancing the training data by reducing the number of

transcriptions for the gender with a greater representation is a valid mitigation technique. However, collecting a sufficient number of representative transcriptions for training may prove difficult for less common languages, including the Slovak language. This problem is exacerbated when also considering different subpopulations which may be subject to bias, such as age groups.

References

- Ardila, R., Branson, M., Davis, K., Kohler, M., Meyer, J., Henretty, M., ... & Weber, G. (2020, May). [Common Voice: A Massively-Multilingual Speech Corpus](#). In *Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference* (pp. 4218-4222).
- Conneau, A., Ma, M., Khanuja, S., Zhang, Y., Axelrod, V., Dalmia, S., ... & Bapna, A. (2023, January). [Fleurs: Few-shot learning evaluation of universal representations of speech](#). In *2022 IEEE Spoken Language Technology Workshop (SLT)* (pp. 798-805). IEEE.
- Feng, S., Kudina, O., Halpern, B. M., & Scharenborg, O. (2021). [Quantifying bias in automatic speech recognition](#). (arXiv:2103.15122). arXiv.
- EIGE. (2013). [A Study of Collected Narratives on Gender Perceptions in the 27 EU Member States](#). Retrieved August 15, 2023.
- Valdrová, J. (2018). *Reprezentace ženství z perspektivy lingvistiky genderových a sexuálních identit*. Slon, 2018. ISBN 9788074192616

6. Data Ethics Assessment

In this chapter, we will discuss the *data ethics assessment* conducted between February and April 2023. This assessment was carried out under the guidance of researchers from the Ethics and Human Values in Technology team. The primary objective of the assessment was to address ethical risks associated with the research tasks in this project, specifically focusing on the data acquisition process. **The primary purpose of the data ethics assessment is to prevent unethical behavior,** ensuring that our research adheres to ethical principles and values throughout its execution. Unethical conduct can result in various negative consequences and ultimately diminish the quality of our scientific research. Moreover, the ethical review process also plays a role in shaping the ethical thinking of researchers and other stakeholders involved in the project.

The term *data acquisition process* refers to a systematic method used to gather, collect, and record data from various sources. This step is fundamental in the data lifecycle as it is essential for analysis, decision-making, and uncovering underlying data patterns.

Data ethics pertains to an ethical domain that assesses practices involving data collection, sharing, and utilization, particularly those that have the potential to negatively affect individuals and society.

Data ethics involves responsibly and sustainably using data to benefit people and society. It centers on ethical data processes that prioritize human well-being. It aligns with human rights and data protection laws, emphasizing transparent data management and the development of privacy-centric products and systems. Treating others' data as you would your own is essential. Data ethics goes beyond legal compliance, ensuring that all data processing meets the standards of GDPR, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and the European Convention on Human Rights (Tranberg et al., 2018).

Data ethics assessments can encompass a range of techniques and methods, from assessing specific datasets to entire projects. Instead of narrowly examining data-related aspects, we adopted a comprehensive approach that also considers broader ethical considerations concerning accountability, communication, and transparency in our project. However, our primary focus was on the data acquisition

process. This approach enabled us to conduct a more thorough evaluation of the project's ethical implications and potential ethical challenges.

Structure and content of the assessment process

For a better understanding of the various ethical and societal issues, we organised several workshops attended by researchers participating in the project tasks, especially those directly working with data. The workshops took the form of facilitated meetings, spanning approximately 2.5 hours.

The assessment process unfolded in several phases, with key elements including the identification of stakeholders and affected persons, the identification of ethical issues, and the creation of a risk register. Following the stakeholder identification phase, we conducted an extra workshop with gender experts whose involvement as stakeholders we deemed meaningful and beneficial at that stage of the assessment and for the overall research. The characteristics of the different parts of the assessment will be elaborated upon in the individual subsections.

Throughout the meetings, attendees had access to presentations, professional materials, and recordings, which were provided for reference and review purposes. The process generated various deliverables, such as a stakeholder matrix and an ethical risk matrix. However, the most significant outcome of this process was the enhanced understanding and heightened sensitivity to ethical issues surrounding the research tasks of the project.

Stakeholders

A stakeholder is a person, group, or organization that will be considerably affected by the project's research tasks, especially the data acquisition process. A better understanding of various stakeholder groups helps research teams or organizations to more easily identify and mitigate ethical and societal risks connected to it. Moreover, stakeholder participation in the research that brings together diverse perspectives can facilitate informed decision-making, enhancing the legitimacy of work with data. By embracing stakeholders' perspectives, research teams or organizations can foster a collaborative environment that encourages transparency and accountability throughout the research process. This inclusive approach ensures that potential concerns and viewpoints are taken into consideration, leading to the

development of more robust and relevant research outcomes. Additionally, involving stakeholders can lead to the creation of tailored communication strategies that effectively convey the project's goals, methodologies, and potential impacts to a wider audience. The goal of the stakeholder identification is not only to help us identify more specific potential risks but also to identify stakeholders that could be potentially involved in the process.

Types of stakeholders

We distinguish two important groups of stakeholders:

Direct stakeholders – those who are involved or directly affected by the project's research tasks. They typically have a more immediate and tangible connection to these tasks (e.g., data acquisition process) and their outcomes.

Indirect stakeholders – while not directly involved in the project's research tasks, indirect stakeholders can still be affected by their implications and outcomes. Their connection to assessed work with data may be more secondary or derived.

Regarding the research process we have identified the following most prominent groups of direct stakeholders:

- **Research team** – KInIT researchers involved in research tasks.
- **Bias researchers** – Researchers with expertise in bias or gender stereotypes who provide advice or otherwise collaborate to meet the objectives of the project's research tasks.
- **Dataset creators** – Persons who design the data gathering process and create datasets for the research purposes of the project.
- **Dataset contributors** – Persons who actively contribute to the data (e.g., stereotypical sentences) in the data gathering process to create datasets for the research purposes of the project.
- **Data annotators** – Persons who comment on and evaluate the data, rather than gather or create them (cf. dataset creators, data contributors).

The most prominent indirect stakeholders include **AI system owners**, **AI system users** or **language experts**.

Stakeholder matrix

In order to identify a larger set of direct and indirect stakeholders, the identification process was enriched with two additional factors:

Impact – a degree of foreseeable benefits and harms of the project's research tasks on the stakeholder group.

Awareness – a degree to which the stakeholder is aware and sensitive to foreseeable benefits and harms.

Such analysis results in the stakeholder matrix providing a clear categorization of affected groups with guidance on what communication strategies to consider in order to increase the general transparency of the project's research tasks:

- **Engage (dataset creators, research team, bias researchers)** – Highly impacted stakeholders with high awareness. Effort must be made to engage these stakeholders in the research process in order to understand their needs correctly and to have the first feedback on the countermeasures devised by the research team to mitigate the most severe ethical and societal risks.
- **Raise (data contributors, data annotators, system owners, professional AI system users)** – Highly impacted stakeholders with low awareness. Even if not involved directly in the process, the research team should know how they perceive the impact of the research on their lives. This group of stakeholders should be kept informed and made aware of the impact research has on them.
- **Explain (language experts, grant agency/donor)** – Low-impacted stakeholders but with high awareness and sensitivity. If the awareness of these stakeholders is high, there must be a reason. They might often have important information, perspectives, or experiences, but may lack the capacity to make their voices heard because the possible impacts on them do not appear to be severe. This group of stakeholders should be kept informed to keep their level of interest and awareness high.
- **Review (casual AI system users, data infrastructure providers, non-binary people)** – Low-impacted stakeholders with low awareness and sensitivity. These stakeholders do not necessarily need to be engaged at the moment, but it is important to monitor and review their situation because their status can change.

Online workshop Gender bias in AI

The goal of stakeholder identification was not only to help us identify more specific potential risks but also to identify stakeholders that could be potentially involved in the process. One of the essential outcomes of the stakeholder analysis was the call for the involvement of people with gender expertise as important stakeholders. They participated in the assessment process and in fulfilling some of the project's objectives.

In pursuit of an interdisciplinary approach, an online workshop was held in March 2023, which was attended by gender experts in addition to KInIT researchers. The main goal of the meeting was to gain lessons and guidance regarding a more professional consideration of the topic of gender stereotypes in the project. We needed to validate whether there exists a representative list of gender stereotypes in Slovakia or a corpus of linguistic expressions containing gender prejudices, which could be further explored through experimental work. The knowledge gained and the information resources provided should contribute to project outputs and would lead to a better understanding of gender biases in Slovakia.

The content of the workshop included the presentation of the project and related research activities, including planned experiments, as well as an introduction to the issue of language models based on AI. The subsequent discussion on methodological aspects of the research and the nature of gender bias provided an opportunity to compare and enrich our perspectives on the subject.

As a result of the discussion, we found out, for example, that although there is no representative corpus of linguistic expressions containing gender prejudices in the Slovak language, it is possible to compile a list of gender stereotypes using various sources (e.g., EIGE, 2013). This list served as a basis for creating datasets containing various linguistic expressions intended for testing language models based on AI.

Assessment list

An ethics-based assessment list in the context of project's research tasks refers to a structured framework of questions or checklist of criteria designed to evaluate and assess the ethical implications and considerations associated especially with the data acquisition process. It helps to identify various ethical issues that may arise from data collection, use, and publication. It can be used by researchers, AI

developers, organizations, policymakers, and regulatory bodies to evaluate the ethical implications of data. Regardless of its specific variations, every assessment list should aim to evaluate and ensure the ethical implications and considerations of data work practices, ultimately fostering responsible and accountable data research practices.

We have used a *data ethics* assessment list as a tool used for the ethical evaluation and assessment of a project's research tasks. Our assessment list consisted of a set of questions gathered from various sources, namely the Data Ethics Canvas (Tarrant, 2021), Data Ethics Framework (GOV.UK, 2020), and Data Ethics Impact Assessment (DataEthics.eu, 2021), tailored to address especially the ethical considerations related to data usage in research. The 24 areas of questions from the assessment list were discussed with participants who took part in the evaluation process as part of a series of workshops.

The following sections include topics and a selected set of related questions from the aforementioned assessment list that were discussed during the assessment. Please note that the set of questions provided here is not exhaustive. It serves as a curated selection of questions that have been chosen based on their relevance and relationship to the assessed project's tasks. See Appendix A for a complete list of all questions and their corresponding answers.

First, we brought into the debate questions that specifically addressed our research motivations, goals, potential benefits as well as the risks associated with it. These included these areas: *Reasons for using data*, *Beneficiality of data use*, *Positive effects*, *Harmed stakeholders* and *Possible harms*. The debate revolved around the ethical and societal aspects of data collection and usage in a project. It covered topics such as the project's primary purpose for data collection, its impact on society, inclusivity and reducing inequalities, potential harm to certain groups, and the risk of data misuse and ethical concerns. Overall, the discussion aimed to ensure responsible and ethical data practices while maximizing societal benefits and minimizing harm.

The most discussed questions were:

- What is your primary purpose for collecting and using data in this project?
- Are you making things better for society? How and for whom?

- Which individuals, groups, demographics, or organizations will be positively affected by this project? How?
- Who could be negatively affected or harmed by this project?
- Could the misuse of the data/algorithm or poor design of the project contribute to reinforcing social and ethical problems and inequalities?

We continued with the topics of transparency, diversity and accountability. These included these areas: *Communicating purpose, Responsibility, Diversity and opinion sharing* and *Auditability*. The debate revolved around ensuring understanding and clarity in project communication, particularly for non-experts. Transparency in decision-making processes was also discussed, along with the benefits of diversity within the project team and how to encourage diverse perspectives. Additionally, the conversation touched on the importance of allowing different opinions and sharing project-related information transparently. Finally, the debate considered the role of peer feedback and effective internal communication for project improvement.

The most discussed questions were:

- How will you communicate your purpose? Will this communication be clear?
- Will you explain what your project does and how it was designed in plain language to a non-expert audience (not only data collection, but also the research design, analysis tools, and algorithms you are using)?
- Did you define who does what in the project? Who is responsible for crucial decisions? Are they capable of explaining their decision?
- How have you ensured diversity in your team?

We also paid particular attention to the data governance and control of data. This is the area of *Rights around data* with the following questions:

- Are individuals and/or organizations providing the data aware of how it will be used?
- Do you have permission to use the data, or other basis on which you are allowed to use the data? What ongoing rights will the data source have?

The questions in the assessment sheet were designed to help everyone involved in the assessment process to debate the issues, there was space to comment verbally and in writing on the questions. These debates prepared us for the risk management stage.

Risk management

Risk refers to the potential for harm, negative consequences, or undesirable outcomes arising from specific actions, decisions, or events. Ethical risk, in the context of research, pertains to the potential harm or negative impact on ethical principles, values, or considerations associated with the research process. Management of ethical risks and countermeasures narrows the gap between abstract principles and practice and at the same time increases the chances of implementing more ethical and trustworthy choices in the research process (Bruschi & Diomedede, 2023).

A risk-based approach allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of potential ethical risks in research. By identifying and assessing risks, the assessment process prioritized critical areas for examination, ensuring significant ethical concerns are adequately addressed. Our aim was to ensure that ethical risks linked to the project's research tasks are effectively identified, addressed, and managed.

The management of ethical risks involved a three-step approach. The first step was risk identification, where potential ethical risks associated with the project's research tasks were systematically identified and analyzed. The second step involved risk evaluation and the third step proposal of possible countermeasures to mitigate those risks. To facilitate this process, we employed a risk matrix framework that enhances the categorization of ethical risks based on their relationship to specific stakeholders. The register of ethical risks based on this matrix helped us in determining the priority of actionable steps that should be taken to address the identified risks effectively.

We evaluated ethical risks within four dimensions:

- **Exposure to stakeholder groups** – We used an exposure range from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest (affecting only individuals) and 5 is the highest (affecting almost the entire population) exposure of stakeholders to impacts.
- **Likelihood of ethical risks** – The likelihood is the probability of negative consequences. It represents the probability that adverse consequences of a certain risk might occur. We used a probability range from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest (almost impossible) and 5 is the highest (almost certain) probability.

- **Severity of impacts on stakeholders** – The severity of the expected consequences is estimated by considering the amount of negative impact on stakeholders. We used severity of impacts ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest (negligible) and 5 is the highest (catastrophic) severity.
- **Type of action organizations could provide** – There are risks that can be effectively mitigated, but there are also some risks that will be only partially under our control or even outside our reach. Therefore, we evaluated the level of control when mitigating these risks.
 - **Act:** Risk mitigation is within the control of the participants.
 - **Influence:** Mitigation of this risk is not fully under control, but some outcomes may be influenced.
 - **Monitor:** This risk is completely beyond control, all that can be done is to monitor the consequences.

Examples of risks

We identified a total of 16 risks. The examples of the most imminent ethical risks that we have identified and evaluated are presented in the following sections. For each risk, we also outlined proposed countermeasures that could mitigate the potential impacts of the risk or avoid it altogether.

Very High Risks

Unclear crowdsourcing instructions

- If the instructions are not clear, the annotators might not be able to generate satisfactory examples of sentences or might abandon the activity altogether. This can reduce the quality of the dataset and the results of the experiment, thus negatively affecting the trustworthiness of our activities.
- As a possible countermeasure we decided to use paid expert annotators and to communicate the risks present in the risk register to them during coordination meetings. For example, among other things, we have guided them to work independently to ensure the quality of the outputs. The annotators had the opportunity to consult with us on any issues related to their work throughout.

Lack of participant representativeness

- Non-representative demographic composition and lack of proper expertise of participants or annotators could lead to a biased dataset. This might lead to inaccurate results that do not necessarily reflect how language and the systems in question are used in real life situations.
- A possible countermeasure is to have a clear data acquisition methodology and to be transparent about the limitations of the research. We involved women and men with different expertise in the creation of the dataset, but always relevant to the nature of the task at hand.

Misuse of data

- The data we collect could be misused for various purposes, such as training intentionally stereotypical and offensive models. This can lead to harms to the involved individuals, breaching their privacy or autonomy, or harm to the entire democratic society.
- We suggested that this risk should be considered especially when publishing data. Consideration should be given to accessing sensitive data only on request, which would require identification and expression of intent for the use of the data.

High Risks

Lack of conceptual clarity

- Definitions of key concepts such as fairness, bias, or discrimination can vary across disciplines and can be highly contested. If our understanding and communication of these concepts is not unified and widely agreeable, it might lead to inaccurate evaluation of experiments, and consequently to false or misleading conclusions drawn from the experiments.
- As a countermeasure to this risk we organized an extra workshop where we discussed various concepts and definitions of fairness and their implications, and how they related to our research and experiments. We agreed that in terms of different definitions of algorithmic fairness, we are interested in concepts of group fairness and distributive fairness in this research.

Evaluation bias

- We do not include some important variations of gender distinctions in a language (e.g., non-binary) where gender bias appears. There is a chance we might overlook (or overemphasize) some socio-cultural aspects of gender bias in Slovakia, when creating examples of gender stereotypes. That can lead to gaps or omissions in the evaluation of experiments that will not cover some important aspects of gender bias in Slovak AI, by reducing the quality and reproducibility of our research.
- As a possible countermeasure we suggested proactively articulating the scope and constraints of our work. We organized a workshop with top experts in the field to tackle gender bias. Together, we identified and listed key gender stereotypes, gathering input from the experts to ensure accuracy. Our main goal was to make sure everyone involved in creating datasets understood these stereotypes. We also maintained an open channel for ongoing feedback from dataset creators to keep improving our work.

Exposure to harmful and offensive data

- Some of the data might contain stereotypical statements about men or women, which might be considered offensive, leading to psychological harm for data creators, contributors, and annotators.
- As a possible countermeasure we communicated this especially to the annotators. In case of a problem, they had the opportunity to communicate their worries regarding their well-being with the project task leader or to withdraw from the task at any time.

Unintended use of data beyond the original purpose

- Some activities within the experiments such as playing the obtained recordings to speech recognition systems/uploading them to platforms could go beyond the original informed consent from participants. This might violate their individual privacy rights and lead to legal consequences. Also, when we need to collect data beyond the original purpose and it will not be clear to the stakeholders why exactly we need to collect those specific types of data in the project, this may lead to a lack of trust from them.
- Consideration of this risk and our capacity to put effective countermeasures led us not to conduct an experiment that would collect audio recordings.

Misinterpretation of the project

- Given the somewhat sensitive nature of the topic at hand, some actors might misinterpret our research results for various political or ideological reasons. This may provoke negative reactions from a part of the society with regard to a sensitive topic and lead to increased tensions and polarization in society.
- We reasoned that the manner of communication and the subject matter should be sufficiently thoughtful. We developed a thorough communication plan that involved sharing project details on the KInIT website and social media, discussing research findings with selected media outlets, and presenting the research and its results at the project's final event.

Low reusability and reproducibility

- For various reasons, such as the design of experiments or API updates of the services used, the results of our experiments might change after some time. This can lead to overall problems with reproducibility, leading other researchers to not being able to validate our results.
- We have suggested several countermeasures including our engagement in comprehensive discussions to assess the reproducibility of each experiment, recognizing potential challenges like the impact of API service updates on experimental outcomes, the establishment of a rigorous validation process to ensure alignment with research objectives, conduct of a thorough examination of pitfalls outlined in existing literature, and meticulous documentation of the software tool, library, and API versions utilized in our experiments to enhance transparency and reproducibility.

False generalizations

- If our methodology, its limitations and communication strategy is not clearly defined, we might make false generalizations. This can lead to, for example, creating unfairly negative reputation of the platforms analysed in our project by suggesting that they are not doing enough to remedy gender biases even if in fact they are trying to.
- As a possible countermeasure, we recommended transparent communication of the limitations of our experiments, seeking input from experts in various domains, and committed to openly acknowledge and avoid unsupported or

generic statements. These measures collectively enhanced the credibility and integrity of our research efforts.

References

Bruschi, D., & Diomedede, N. (2023). [A framework for assessing AI ethics with applications to cybersecurity](#). *AI and Ethics*, 3(1), 65–72.

DataEthics.eu (2021). [Data Ethics Impact Assessment 2021](#). Retrieved August 31, 2023.

EIGE. (2013). [A Study of Collected Narratives on Gender Perceptions in the 27 EU Member States](#). Retrieved August 31, 2023.

GOV.UK. (2020, September 20). [Data Ethics Framework](#). Retrieved August 31, 2023.

Tarrant, D., Maddison, J., & Thereaux, O. (2021, June 28). [The Data Ethics Canvas](#). The Open Data Institute. Retrieved August 21, 2023.

Tranberg, P., Hasselbalch, G., Olsen, K., & Byrne, C. S. (2018). DATAETHICS – Principles and Guidelines for Companies, Authorities & Organisations.

Appendix A. Assessment List

Area	Question
Reasons for using data	What is your primary purpose for collecting and using data in this project?
Benevolence of data use	Are you making things better for society? How and for whom? Do you ensure that primarily users benefit from their own data – not just the organization? How does the project work towards advancing human capabilities, advancing inclusion of underrepresented populations, reducing economic, social, gender, racial, and other inequalities?
Positive effects	Which individuals, groups, demographics or organizations will be positively affected by this project? How? How are you measuring positive impact? How could you increase it?
Harmed stakeholders	Who could be negatively affected or harmed by this project? What are the groups that would be disadvantaged by the project/that would not benefit from the project?
Possible harms	Could the misuse of the data/algorithm or poor design of the project contribute to reinforcing social and ethical problems and inequalities?
Minimising negative impact	What steps can you take to minimize these harms? How are you measuring, reporting and acting on potential negative impacts of your project? What kind of mechanisms can you put in place to prevent this from happening?
Communicating purpose	Do stakeholders understand your purpose? How will you communicate your purpose? Will this communication be clear? Will you explain what your project does and how it was designed in plain language to a non-expert audience (not only data collection, but also about the research design, analysis tools, and algorithms you are using)? How are you ensuring most vulnerable individuals or stakeholder groups understand?
Auditability	Could you publish your methodology, metadata, datasets, code or impact measurements? Can you ask peers for feedback on the project? How will you communicate it internally?

Engaging with people	<p>How can people engage with you about the project?</p> <p>How can people correct information, appeal or request changes to the product/service? Are these mechanisms reasonable and well understood?</p>
Responsibility	<p>Have you defined who does what in the project? Who is responsible for crucial decisions? Is he capable of explaining his decision?</p> <p>What is the mechanism of approval, rejection, or refinement of his decision?</p>
Diversity and opinion sharing	<p>How have you ensured diversity in your team? Having a diverse team helps prevent biases and encourages more creativity and diversity of thought.</p> <p>How can people with different opinions and backgrounds express themselves?</p>
Reproducibility	<p>If necessary, how can you (or external scrutiny) validate that the algorithm is achieving the correct output decision when new data is added?</p> <p>How can you demonstrate that you have designed the project for reproducibility?</p> <p>Could another analyst repeat your procedure based on your documentation? Have they tried?</p>
Data Sources reliability	<p>Are you collecting and annotating data yourself or accessing via third parties? By humans or machines? Are you aware of possible aberrations from reality?</p> <p>Are these data sources reliable and trustworthy? How do you validate their reliability and quality?</p>
Data quality and representability	<p>Are there limitations that could influence your project's outcomes?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - bias in data collection, inclusion/exclusion, analysis, algorithms - gaps or omissions in data - provenance, geographic, demographic or historical limitations <p>What measures have you taken to mitigate these limitations?</p> <p>Is the data used for your research representative for our purpose? Which groups are not represented?</p>
Fair sources	<p>Was the data collected for this project or for another purpose?</p> <p>Was the data acquired by fair and honest means?</p>
Personal and sensitive data	<p>Is any personal data involved, or data that is otherwise sensitive for stakeholders? What legislation, policies, or other regulations shape how you use data? What requirements do they introduce?</p>
Open data	<p>If data is non-sensitive, non-personal, and if Data Sharing Agreements with the supplier allow it, will you make the data open?</p>

Store limitation	<p>How long will you hold the (in particular sensitive) data?</p> <p>Will you hold these data for longer than is required to achieve your purpose?</p>
Behavioral design	<p>Do you use data to influence user behavior? Can you mislead other users' behavior by your actions?</p> <p>Do you ensure that the design does not create addiction and thus influences the person's self-determination and empowerment?</p>
Acceptance of data use	<p>Will the people agree about using the data for this purpose? What stakeholder groups could be worried or feel uncomfortable?</p> <p>How have you shared your understanding of the stakeholders' attitude with them?</p>
Rights around data	<p>Are individuals and/or organizations providing the data aware of how it will be used?</p> <p>Do you have permission to use this data, or other basis on which you're allowed? What ongoing rights will the data source have?</p>
Re-identification	<p>Could the way that data is collected, used or shared cause harm or risk individuals being re-identified?</p> <p>How can you demonstrate that the data has been de-identified to the greatest degree possible? Can the data be matched to any other datasets that will make individuals easily identifiable? What measures have you taken to mitigate this?</p>
Sharing data	<p>Are you going to be sharing sensitive data with other organizations? If so, which ones?</p> <p>Are you planning to publish any of the data?</p> <p>Under what conditions?</p>
Proportionality and data minimization	<p>Is the input data suitable and necessary to achieve the aim? Would the proposed use of data be deemed inappropriate by those who provided the data (individuals and/or organizations)?</p> <p>Is there another way to achieve the same outcome? How will you ensure data minimization?</p>

About Us

Kempelen Institute of Intelligent Technologies (KInIT) is an independent, non-profit research institute that conducts cutting-edge research on intelligent technologies, primarily focusing on artificial intelligence and its intersections with other disciplines. KInIT aims to accelerate the economic transformation of Slovakia by conducting excellent research in artificial intelligence and its innovative applications. Drawing inspiration from leading institutions in other countries, KInIT serves as a center of expertise that encourages companies to engage in research, strengthens their connections with the academic sector, and attracts talent to Slovakia.

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